

Which apparent magnitude produces a count rate of 100 Hz?

L Lindegren 1997 July 15 (gaia_ll_5)

The table gives the V, R and I magnitudes (Cousins' system) for various spectral types that will produce a count rate of 100 electrons per second.

Assumptions:

- two circular pupils of 0.6 m diameter each
- optical transmittance 0.8 (at all wavelengths)
- quantum efficiency as for EEV 42 Series CCD (300–1050 nm, max QE=0.85)
- stellar spectral curves from Gunn & Stryker, normalised to flux density $3.69E-23$ W/m²/Hz at 550 nm for unreddened A0V star of magnitude V=0 (Straizys, Multicolor Stellar Photometry, 1992)
- standard extinction law also from Straizys (1992)
- V, R, I response curves from Bessell (PASP 95, 480, 1983)

Sp	A_V=0			A_V=5		
	V	R	I	V	R	I
B0Ib	20.71	20.85	21.04	21.09	20.26	19.44
B1V	20.70	20.86	21.03	21.08	20.25	19.42
A0V	20.54	20.55	20.56	21.28	20.31	19.34
A5V	20.54	20.41	20.27	21.48	20.36	19.26
F6V	20.59	20.33	20.08	21.65	20.39	19.20
G2V	20.63	20.28	19.93	21.80	20.44	19.18
G8III	20.69	20.18	19.73	22.01	20.51	19.16
K3V	20.72	20.18	19.73	22.02	20.49	19.16
K3III	20.88	20.16	19.55	22.33	20.61	19.14
M0V	21.12	20.19	19.38	22.64	20.72	19.09
M0III	21.09	20.21	19.39	22.66	20.77	19.12
M8V	22.14	20.77	19.00	24.12	21.48	19.11
M7III	23.64	21.41	19.10	25.80	22.18	19.43

Conclusion:

An integration time of 2.5 s will produce >100 photoelectrons at I=20 for any spectral type and any reddening (up to at least A_V=5).

Whether this is sufficient to detect the star will depend on the background noise (RON, sky, and confusion) and requires further evaluation.